

Development and Implementation of Material Requirements Planning with Payment Tracking System for Company XYZ

William Chan
University of Asia and the Pacific
Pasig City, Metro Manila,
1605
Philippines
william.chan@uap.asia

Peter Lim
University of Asia and the Pacific
Pasig City, Metro Manila,
1605
Philippines
peter.lim@uap.asia

Isabella Molo
University of Asia and the Pacific
Pasig City, Metro Manila,
1605
Philippines
isabella.molo@uap.asia

Rommel Deocarlis
University of Asia and the Pacific
Pasig City, Metro Manila,
1605
Philippines
rommel.deocarlis@uap.asia

ABSTRACT

The researchers discovered that Company XYZ has been experiencing multiple problems in regards to planning projects. Company XYZ currently uses Microsoft Excel to record their suppliers and materials in their inventory. The proposed system for Company XYZ was implemented using an Agile Driven Approach wherein the researchers would consistently update and interview the client in order to potentially improve on the proposed solution and discover underlying conflicts between the actions of the researchers and the company. The proposed system will allow Company XYZ to keep track of their inventory, quickly search for suppliers, keep track of accounts payables, and overall, make effective decisions to minimize expenses and maximize profits through better planning.

KEYWORDS

Inventory, Suppliers, Payment Tracking, Accounts Receivables, Agile, Planning, Construction, MRP

1. INTRODUCTION

Company XYZ is a construction company that has been in the industry for 32 years. They are open to doing any type of construction project, with the exception of government projects. On the researchers meeting with the company, they were informed that they manually encode their data in Microsoft Excel to keep track of their inventory, suppliers, and disbursement forms. The other parts of their business process they keep track of on paper. According to the company, although this system has worked for them, it is incredibly time consuming and inefficient. This inefficiency causes them to lose potential customers and lessens the amount of profit they gain from a project.

The researchers were tasked with a way to reduce the inefficiency in the company's current system. The company also requested that the system be very simple and easy to learn and use. This is because some of the company employees are older and not very adept with technology—one of the reasons they have used the same manual system for 32 years. The company stated that they would like to have their system automated and improved on, but they are worried about how they would adapt to it. This is why the researchers decided to look into the agile method of development.

The agile methodology is based on iterative and incremental development [1]. According to Kumar and Bhatia [1]: “Agile software development takes the view that production teams should start with simple and predictable approximations to the final requirement and then continue to increment the detail of these requirements throughout the life of the development. This incremental requirements refinement further refines the design, coding and testing at all stages of production activity. In this way, the requirements work product is as accurate and useful as the final software itself.” The researchers decided that this approach was best for both them and the company. This is because this project was a first attempt for the researchers at delivering a fully functioning system. Agile methodology also allows the researchers to implement any changes needed much faster, thus saving time.

At the end of each sprint in the agile development method, the researchers showed the progress of the system being developed to the company. This way, not only could the company provide feedback, but it also gave them time to get accustomed to the system and how it works. The researchers took their feedback into account to improve the system and make it easier to use and learn for other employees of the company when they start using it.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Material Requirements Planning (MRP) systems can be used to ensure that materials are available for production or products are ready to be delivered to customers, and also for planning transactions and delivery schedules. The Material Requirements Planning (MRP) system maximizes the utilization of resources, thus effectiveness and efficiency is observed in its usage [2].

Multiple advantages can be listed down when using a Materials Requirement Planning (MRP) system some of which is that construction companies will be able to maintain priorities updated and valid, easily adjust to the change of requirements and late deliveries, a change in a customer's order quantity or timing, and unexpected scrap results from manufacturing. With the use of an MRP system, planning production will be efficient in terms of laying out the right materials at the required place and time [3].

Lastly, the Material Requirements Planning (MRP) system contains packages such as the Inventory Management System and a Supplier Database containing information on materials distinguished by unique IDs. These features of the proposed system provide capabilities such as being able to organize materials physically and virtually through the use of unique IDs, provide data on the availability and unavailability of materials, and produce a central database as a point of reference for all the suppliers and the materials needed for a project [4].

Pyramid Construction Ltd. specializes in heavy construction, general contracting, and land deployment at the start of their business, they partnered with Geac, an accounting management software, which does not integrate well with the functional areas of the company. In 2002, Pyramid Construction partnered up with Jonas Construction Software, which is the integration of an Inventory Management System and a Supplier Tracking History (Day, n.d.). According to the controller of Pyramid Construction, Gerrie Day [5], “With Jonas, we are able to keep track of our materials and our inventory. Our accounting staff has even been reduced by 60% and work has been really efficient”. Some of the features of Jonas Construction Software include: (1) Quick and easy searches; (2) Complete Inventory Management; (3) Inventory Tracking System; and (4) Procurement [5]. In addition, the system allows the user to Easily search and locate inventory on hand and determine which pieces of inventory are attached to specific work orders, and also search for price per unit and count remaining [5]. Furthermore, the construction inventory management software handles multi-warehouse, bill of material, serialization, UPC tracking, and supplier history tracking. It can easily receive inventory, with the ability to buy in one unit of measure and sell in another [5]. The system is also capable of managing the intricacies associated with maintaining costs, optimal stock levels and effective reporting. Their construction inventory management software keeps track of inventory on hand, minimum and maximum inventory counts, bill of materials, and tracks what you purchase from multiple suppliers [5]. Lastly, it allows the user to merge an inventory reorder list based on stocking levels to automatically create purchase orders. When inventory reaches the set minimum amount, stock is automatically ordered based on your threshold level set [5].

The Construction Journal and Payment Tracking System, in line with the proposed system, will enable a user to keep track of projects and their cost and profit. In addition, the Construction Journal uses a tagging system. When a search request is entered with keywords for items of interest, the search result lists entries from tags containing those keywords. This saves a user time in finding and keeping track of projects, their materials, prices, and payments [6].

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the researchers were to:

- Identify the reason/s behind the company’s inefficiency.
- Propose a system design to solve or reduce the inefficiency.

4. METHODOLOGY

This section will discuss the methods and actions taken during the creation and implementation of the system.

4.1 Research Design

The researchers used the Agile Development method in order for any feedback or changes requested by the client to be implemented quickly and with ease. This method also ensures that the researchers are constantly updating the client on the progress of the system. An end of sprint report is made after each sprint to show that the deliverables are being met and to account for any changes to the upcoming sprints.

4.2 Research Participants

The researchers interviewed the Chief Operating Officer (COO), three of the employees handling the inventory and suppliers of the company, and one employee handling accounting.

4.3 Data-Gathering Procedure

The researchers interviewed the Chief Operating Officer (COO) as well as specific employees to get a better understanding of the company’s business process and problems. Due to the current situation with the pandemic, not all of the researchers were able to visit the company to get a better understanding of their workflow.

Since the researchers used the agile development method, they divided the project into four sprints. Each sprint lasted one month. Scrum meetings were held twice a week on Wednesdays and Saturdays for around 15-30 minutes each. This was for each member of the team to update each other on their current progress, gauge the overall progress of the system, as well as resolve any issues or problems the team may be facing.

End-of-Sprint meetings were held near the end of each sprint. This was so that the team could ascertain whether the sprint goals were met, plan for the next sprint, and consult with the client on any feedback or changes to the system.

4.4 Treatment of Data

With the qualitative data gathered from all the interviews, the researchers were able to understand the business process of the company despite the limitations due to the pandemic. Client feedback was discussed and addressed as

soon as possible or in the following sprint. The client gave evaluation scores of the systems to the researchers under strict confidentiality. 1 being strongly disagree, 2 being disagree, 3 being neutral, 4 being agree, and 5 being strongly agree. The researchers got the average score of each category to determine the client's overall satisfaction with the system. The higher the score, the more satisfied the client is with the system.

4.5 Validation

The researchers developed a prototype based on the system design and constraints proposed to and approved by the client. At the end of each sprint, the researchers are met with the client to show their progress, and any implemented changes based on feedback from the previous sprint. The researchers also discussed with the client any problems they encountered and gave suggestions to change or implement into the system, if any.

An evaluation was given to the client in order to assess the system. These are based on (1) User Friendliness, (2) Security, (3) Reliability, (4) Efficiency, (5) Acceptability, (6) Adaptability, and (7) Robustness. Each category is rated on a scale from (1) to (5), with (1) being the lowest and (5) being the highest. The evaluation made use of the Likert scale. The average of all the evaluation metrics was taken to assess the client's overall satisfaction with the system per sprint.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on Table 1, the business process of Company XYZ is project based. They must find the materials needed for the project based on the request of the client that is of quality at the best possible price point. They show their client a quotation, and if the client agrees, the deal is closed. The price stated on the quotation is something the company has to follow. Since the company cannot purchase the materials until the deal is closed and the availability of items on the market is fast-changing, they have to be very careful with the price they state on the quotation and be prepared in case they need to find a new supplier for the materials they need. Their system is also manual, so it can take them a long time to gather the information needed to make a quotation form, especially since they have to be very careful to not make any errors, since any errors can lead to a loss in profit.

Table 1. Interview and Observations

INTERVIEW	
Question 1: What is the nature of your business?	Answer 1: We are a project based construction company.

	Project based means that we do projects based on the request of our clients. We are open to doing all kinds of projects, except government projects.
Question 2: What is your business process from start to finish of closing a deal on a project?	Answer 2: After we receive a request from a client, we send some of our employees to check it out to see if it's feasible for us to take. Then we contact our workers to see who is available and come up with a list of supplies we need. If we do not have the supplies in our inventory, we look for a supplier. Based on all this information, we make a quotation and show it to the client. If the client approves, then the deal is closed.
Question 3: How do you usually keep track of your projects, inventory, etc?	Answer 3: We do most things manually. For the more complicated things with more information such as our inventory and our suppliers, we use Microsoft Excel to keep track of them.
Question 4: Have you encountered any problems keeping track of things this way?	Answer 4: Well, it can take a long time for us to find the information we need sometimes.
Question 5: Have these delays had a significant negative impact on your company?	Answer 5: It does not have much of an impact when we don't receive many requests. However, when we receive a lot of requests, it becomes hard to manage them all. Since we come up with a quotation before closing a deal, we have to make sure we really find the best materials at the best price and quality. And because of the availability

	of materials on the market, prices change and are not always available. We have to be very careful since we need to stick to the amount on the quotation, and we cannot purchase the materials until the deal has been closed.
OBSERVATIONS	
Observation 1:	The company's current system is very tedious and leaves room for many errors. This is especially dangerous, since any errors may cause them to incur a loss in profit.
Observation 2:	Because the company's current system is very tedious, it can take them some time to come up with the quotation form needed to close a deal.

The current system of Company XYZ is inefficient and prone to errors. Based on Table 2, company XYZ need a system with functions to minimize misinformation, delays, and inefficiencies from start to finish of a project through proper planning. Since it takes them a lot of time to come up with a quotation, the system should provide them with an estimate based on past projects with similar specifications. The company can use this as a reference in coming up with a quotation, and minimize the time spent in doing so. The system will also work similarly if materials are suddenly no longer available from the supplier after having already closed the deal. It can suggest alternative suppliers so the company can look at all their options to find the best alternative. The system should also have functions to ensure that the user knows what he or she is inputting to minimize accidental misinformation due to human error.

Table 2. Problems and Resolutions

Problems	Resolutions
Delays and inefficiencies in making the quotation	The system can quickly provide data from past projects to suggest materials, suppliers, and come up with a quotation estimate.
Project delays and profit	The system can quickly

losses due to the sudden unavailability of materials	provide alternative suppliers for the materials needed.
Accidental misinformation due to human error	The system will have a simple, user-friendly interface with functions to ensure that the user is certain of the information that is inputted.

5.1 Software Context

Software Context diagram shows how the system is structured and operates logically through its flow of information and interaction between entities and its parts.

Figure 1. Software Context

5.1 Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 2 shows the different entities that the researchers deemed necessary and developed for the system for data storage and retrieval from the system. These entities are shown through tables with different attributes such as primary and foreign keys that pertain to the data and information needed to connect and distinguish each of them from each other.

Figure 2. Entity Relationship Diagram

6. CLIENT FEEDBACK

The data in Table 3 shows the feedback from the client.

Table 3. Client Remarks

Sprint	Client Remarks
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remove the brand field. - No need for images. - Give a user the ability to change the color of the text or the box in a field.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Merge the name, item code, material, and description fields into one field. - Remove the expiration and used fields.
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is better to have a search bar/filter per column instead of one for everything. - Capitalize MOQ. - Add office hours and pickup time to supplier info. - Make it possible to add multiple branches for each supplier.
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change the name Accountant to Accounts. - Some headings

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are unreadable. - Add job order # and project field; remove permit field.
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Based on the scores given by the company from the final sprint as shown below in Table 4, the average score of the system is 4.93. The weakest point is its acceptability. Although the company said that they are satisfied with how the system turned out, they believe it can still be modified in the future as they improve their business process.

Table 4: Final Sprint Scores

Criteria:	Mean Score (out of 5):
User Friendliness	5
Security	5
Reliability	5
Efficiency	5
Acceptability	4.5
Adaptability	5
Robustness	5
Overall Average:	4.93

7. CONCLUSION

The researchers were able to identify issues in the company, and decided that the Agile Methodology approach would be best in solving these issues. These issues are: Delays and inefficiencies in making quotations, project delays and profit losses due to the sudden unavailability of materials, and accidental misinformation due to human error. Using the agile methodology, the researchers made a material requirements planning system with a payment tracking system to help the company better plan their projects.

8. REFERENCES

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